

SOP Fluorescence In-Situ Hybridisation of environmental microplastics.

1. Introduction and Scope

The main purpose of this imaging analysis is to evaluate the taxonomic and spatial resolution of the microorganisms adhered onto microplastics recovered from water samples via Fluorescence In-Situ Hybridisation (FISH).

2. Principle of the Method

As described in the SOP "Water Column Filtration and Storage", at each sampling location, 100 L – 400 L of water will be filtered, resulting in a concentrate at the cod end of approx. 50 mL. The concentrate will be first split into two fractions (a and b, 25 mL each), both of which will be filtered onto Nylon filters (NFs, pore size 45 µm). Collected MPs will be subject of two major different analysis: a) DNA extraction and b) Imaging (Scanning Electron Microscopy, SEM and Fluorescence In-Situ Hybridisation FISH), and as such filters need to be processed and stored differentially, in an appropriate way for subsequent analysis. Based on the observed microbial presence, the micrographies generated via SEM will inform which samples should be further studied via Fluorescence In-Situ Hybridisation. This SOP describes the protocol to process NFs filters for FISH.

3. Chemicals and Reagents

- 70% Ethanol (EtOH) for sterilisation of equipment.
- Fluorophore-labelled oligonucleotides
- Coverslips
- PBS [0.2M] / EtOH [100% v/v] 50:50 v/v
- EtOH high purity grade 70% v/v, 85% v/v, 100% v/v
- Hybridisation solution (900 mM NaCl, 20 mM Tris pH 7.5, 0.01% SDS, 20% formamide)
- Wash buffer (215 mM NaCl, 20 mM Tris pH 7.5, 5 mM EDTA)
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4. Materials and Equipment

- Nylon filters (45 µm pore size, φ 47 mm)
- Flat tip tweezers
- Gloves
- Falcon tubes (50 mL) for concentrate storage
- Falcon tubes (15 mL) for filter storage
- Gloves
- Confocal microscope

5. Method for microplastics preparation for FISH

5.1 Filters fixation

- 5.1.1 Following antiseptic techniques and immediately after vacuum filtration, the NF for MPs imaging analyses (SEM and FISH) will be stored in a Falcon tube containing enough GA (2.5 % v/v) to cover the filter (approx. 4 mL) for 2 h.
- 5.1.2 Depending on the accessibility to a freeze dryer, imaging filters can be either dehydrated (step 5.2.5) or be transferred from GA, into fresh tubes and stored in 50:50 EtOH 100 % v/v and PBS (0.2 M) and keep at – 20 C.

5.2 Filters dehydration

- 5.2.1 Filters will be transferred into fresh Falcon tubes with EtOH 70 % v/v. After 15 mins, the

EtOH will be discarded and replaced with EtOH 85 % v/v. Following 15 mins more, the EtOH solution will be again discarded and replaced with EtOH 100 % v/v.

5.3 FISH

- 5.3.1 Filters will then be air-dried and incubated in 250 µm of hybridisation solution (900 mM NaCl, 20 mM Tris pH 7.5, 0.01% SDS, 20% formamide and each probe at a final concentration of 2 µM) at 46°C for 3 hr.
- 5.3.2 Filters were then transferred into wash buffer (215 mM NaCl, 20 mM Tris pH 7.5, 5 mM EDTA) at 48°C for 15 min to remove un-bound probe.
- 5.3.3 Samples will be then dipped in ice-cold water, drained, air-dried, and mounted in ProLong Gold Antifade Solution (ThermoFisher) within a frame constructed of Parafilm (Beemis Co.) of the same thickness as the plastic samples? This sample spacer will be embedded between two glass coverslips each 0.17 mm thick to permit imaging of both sides of the samples?
- 5.3.4 Samples will be stored in the dark overnight before imaging with a confocal microscope using an oil immersion objective.

Commented [P1]: Is it possible to do FISH on the MPs themselves instead of on the filters?

6 Documentation

Clear labelling of the samples and micrography files will be required. The labels need to include location, depth, and date of collection.

7 Safety

Researchers have undertaken a Health and Safety lab induction.

8 References

- [Carrillo-Barragan P., 2022, SOP Water column collection, filtration, and sample storage for microbiological analyses of microplastics](#)
[Carrillo-Barragan P., 2022, SOP Scanning Electron Microscopy of environmental microbiological microplastics](#)
[Shlundt et al., 2019, Mol Ecol Resour. 2020;20:620–634, DOI: 10.1111/1755-0998.13119](#)